

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AND CHALLENGES IN LEARNING ITALIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT THE ISMAIL QEMALI UNIVERSITY OF VLORA

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Abstract

As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, the importance of learning foreign languages cannot be overstated. Italian, with its rich cultural heritage and global influence, has gained popularity as a foreign language of choice for students at the Ismail Qemali University of Vlora. However, like any language learning process, there are unique challenges that arise during classroom instruction. In this paper, we will explore the intricacies of classroom management and the problems encountered while learning Italian as a foreign language at the Ismail Qemali University of Vlora. This article provides an exploratory review of classroom management in foreign language education, focusing on the distinct characteristics and its impact on teaching methods and interaction patterns. It emphasizes the teachers' struggles with classroom discipline, students' reluctance, and the inadequacy of previous graduate coursework in preparing them for the challenges they face. The review highlights the impact of using the target language for classroom management and the unique difficulties experienced by language teachers. It suggests the need for more research to better understand the relationship between classroom management and foreign language education, particularly regarding the influence of the target language on managing the classroom. This extensive review delineates foreign language teachers' unique concerns and highlights their need for better preparation to manage the classroom effectively.

Keywords: management, classroom, foreign language, Italian, teacher, students.

Classroom Management

Effective classroom management plays a crucial role in creating an ideal learning environment. It encompasses various components, including establishing rules and expectations, managing student behavior, and fostering an atmosphere conducive to learning. In the context of teaching Italian as a foreign language, classroom management requires additional considerations due to the specific linguistic and cultural challenges involved. Classroom management plays a crucial role in facilitating effective teaching and learning in any educational setting, including foreign language classrooms. It involves creating a conducive environment that promotes academic and social-emotional learning, as well as maximizing instructional time. Effective classroom management techniques not only benefit students academically, but also foster positive social opportunities and contribute to a positive classroom atmosphere. (Taylor & Bhana, 2021). Additionally, classroom management is especially important for foreign language teachers as it can impact their job satisfaction and the overall success of language learning. In the context of learning Italian as a foreign language at the Ismail Qemali University of Vlora, classroom management becomes even more significant. One aspect of classroom management is establishing clear expectations regarding language use. In the case of learning Italian, it is essential to create an immersive environment where students are encouraged to communicate primarily in Italian. This can be achieved through strategies such as using target language labels, setting language use goals, and providing opportunities for authentic communication. Another crucial component of

classroom management is addressing individual learning needs. As students come from diverse backgrounds, they may have varying levels of prior exposure to Italian. Teachers must employ differentiated instruction techniques to accommodate the needs of all learners and provide additional support to those who require it. This can involve incorporating various instructional materials, such as multimedia resources, authentic texts, and language games, to engage students at different proficiency levels.

Challenges in Learning Italian as a Foreign Language

While classroom management plays a vital role in facilitating effective learning, there are inherent challenges specific to learning Italian as a foreign language. These challenges arise due to the linguistic differences between Italian and Albanian, the students' native language, and the cultural disparities between the two countries.

Factors Influencing Motivation

Several factors contribute to students' motivation in learning Italian as a second language. These factors can be categorized into intrinsic and extrinsic factors.

Intrinsic Factors

1. Interest in the Target Culture: Students who have a genuine interest in the Italian culture are more likely to have intrinsic motivation. They may find Italian literature, music, art, or cuisine captivating, which can enhance their learning motivation and engagement.

2. Passion for Travel: Enthusiastic travelers who have plans to visit Italy or interact with Italian speakers during trips are highly motivated to learn the language. They see it as a practical skill that will enhance their

travel experiences and allow them to immerse themselves in the local culture.

3. **Bilingual Background:** Students with a bilingual background, such as growing up in an Italian-speaking household or studying other languages, tend to have a stronger intrinsic motivation towards learning Italian. They have prior experience with the language learning process, which can make learning Italian seem more familiar and less intimidating.

Extrinsic Factors

1. **Teacher Support:** A supportive teacher who creates a positive and engaging learning environment can greatly influence students' motivation. Teachers who demonstrate enthusiasm, provide constructive feedback, and encourage students' efforts can foster a sense of achievement and motivation.

2. **Workload and Assessment:** The way assignments, assessments, and grading are structured can impact students' motivation. A balanced workload that allows students to demonstrate their language skills without feeling excessive pressure can improve their motivation and overall learning experience.

3. **Recognition and Rewards:** Recognizing and rewarding students' achievements, such as certificates, prizes, or opportunities for practical application, can serve as extrinsic motivators. These extrinsic rewards can provide students with a sense of success and encourage them to continue their efforts.

Strategies for Motivating L2 Learners

Teachers can implement various strategies to enhance students' motivation in learning Italian as a second language. Here are some effective strategies:

1. **Create a Supportive Learning Environment:** Creating a positive and comfortable classroom atmosphere where students feel valued and supported is essential for fostering motivation. Encouraging open dialogue, celebrating diversity, and creating opportunities for peer interaction can contribute to students' motivation and a sense of belonging.

2. **Use Authentic Materials and Resources:** Introducing authentic materials such as newspapers, songs, podcasts, or videos can greatly enhance students' motivation. Engaging with real-life language materials and tasks can provide them with meaningful context and relevance, making the learning experience more engaging and enjoyable.

3. **Encourage Self-Motivation and Independence:** Encouraging students to take ownership of their learning by setting goals, creating study plans, and practicing independently can foster intrinsic motivation. Providing opportunities for self-reflection and self-assessment can also encourage students to take ownership of their progress and motivate them towards self-improvement.

4. **Utilize Technology and Multimedia:** Integrating technology and interactive multimedia resources into the language learning process can enhance students' motivation. Online language learning platforms, mobile apps, and interactive games can provide engaging and interactive learning opportunities, making language learning more accessible and engaging.

5. **Offer Opportunities for Real-World Application:** Providing opportunities for practical application,

such as language exchanges, language immersion trips, or language-related projects, can motivate students to learn Italian beyond the classroom. This real-world context can make language learning more relevant and encourage students to engage with the language in meaningful and authentic ways.

Firstly, the grammatical structures of Italian, such as verb conjugations and noun declensions, differ significantly from those of Albanian. These differences can lead to confusion and hinder the acquisition of Italian grammar. To overcome this challenge, teachers must adopt instructional strategies that emphasize explicit grammar instruction, provide ample opportunities for practice, and offer targeted feedback to address individual students' specific needs.

Secondly, the phonetic differences between Italian and Albanian pose a significant challenge for learners. Certain sounds and intonations in Italian may be absent or uncommon in Albanian, leading to difficulties in pronunciation and oral communication. Teachers can address this issue by incorporating pronunciation exercises, utilizing audio-visual materials, and engaging students in authentic speaking activities to enhance their phonetic skills. Moreover, cultural differences between Italy and Albania can impact language learning. Italian culture, history, and social norms play a significant role in language usage and understanding. Students may face challenges in comprehending idiomatic expressions, cultural references, or sociolinguistic nuances. Teachers can mitigate this issue by integrating cultural components into classroom activities, organizing cultural events, and encouraging interactions with Italian speakers through virtual exchanges or study abroad programs. The distinct features of foreign language education can present unique challenges for classroom management compared to other subject areas. One key difference lies in the use of the target language (TL) as the medium of instruction, which is not typically required in other subject areas. This necessitates strategies for encouraging effective communication despite potential language barriers and students' varying levels of language proficiency. Additionally, foreign language instruction often involves interaction patterns such as group work that may be unique to language learning and not necessary for effective instruction in other subjects. The diversity of teaching methods and approaches in language education may impact classroom management skills differently than in other subject areas. While traditional grammar-based methodologies were prevalent in the past, the shift toward more communicative approaches in foreign language teaching has implications for classroom management. Teachers' choices in teaching methods can significantly influence interaction patterns, teacher-student roles, and target language use, which in turn affect classroom management.

In summary, the use of the target language, unique interaction patterns, and diverse teaching methods in foreign language education contribute to distinct challenges and strategies for classroom management compared to other subject areas. These factors require foreign language teachers to carefully consider communication barriers, student interactions, and the impact of

teaching methodologies on classroom management. The conception of classroom management refers to the actions taken to create and maintain a learning environment conducive to successful instruction. It involves establishing and reinforcing rules and procedures, carrying out disciplinary actions, maintaining effective teacher-student relationships, and maintaining an appropriate mental set for management. Essentially, classroom management is viewed as essential to creating an atmosphere in the classroom that allows teaching and learning to occur.

Classroom management is essential for educators to effectively teach and for students to learn in a positive and structured environment. This concept is crucial in addressing various challenges that teachers face, especially in the initial years of teaching, such as classroom discipline, dealing with individual differences, organization of class work, relationships with parents, insufficient teaching materials, and overcrowded classrooms. The literature on classroom management emphasizes the construction of an appropriate atmosphere in the classroom so that teaching and learning can occur. It has evolved from a focus on behavioral management to proactively installing desired procedures and routines, ultimately promoting engagement in learning activities and the development of students' capacities for responsibility and self-regulation. Classroom management is crucial for foreign language teachers, as they must navigate the unique challenges presented by foreign language instruction, such as target language use, interaction patterns, and communicative competence, which can impact the process of managing the classroom.

The historical review of research on classroom management in foreign language education reveals a focus on offering quick prescriptions and practical tips to help language teachers cope with classroom management issues. This historical review highlights the lack of research on classroom management in the field of foreign language education from a theoretical or research perspective, and a reliance on how-to books and practical tips for managing classrooms. The evolution of classroom management approaches from authoritarian to laissez-faire was influenced by both behavioral and ecological studies, emphasizing techniques to increase desired behavior and decrease undesired behavior. The research on classroom management has evolved to promote engagement in learning activities, proactive installation of desired procedures and routines, and the development of student responsibility and self-regulation.

The approaches in foreign language teaching encompass behavioral, linguistic, and interactionist perspectives. Behavioral approaches emphasize observable and measurable language behavior and passive learner reception of environmental pressures. Linguistic approaches focus on the linkage of various stimuli in the environment to internal responses and overt verbal behavior. Interactionist approaches, further divided into cognitive and social interactionist, view language development as a process affected by various factors such as cognitive development and social interaction.

These approaches influence language teaching methodologies, leading to diverse teaching activities and considerations for classroom management. Research suggests that understanding these theoretical approaches is essential for addressing classroom management issues in foreign language education.

The evolution of teaching approaches in foreign language education has seen a shift from grammar-based methodologies to more communicative approaches. Grammar-based methods emphasize grammar rules, translation, and deductive teaching, while communicative approaches focus on learning to communicate and achieving communicative competence through interaction. These changes in teaching methods impact classroom management by influencing student-teacher interactions, participation, and the use of the target language.

Moreover, foreign language teaching involves distinct characteristics that influence classroom management. Effective instruction requires the use of a language that students do not yet understand, necessitates interaction patterns, and employs diverse, student-focused teaching methodologies. These features affect how teachers manage their classrooms and create specific challenges related to students' language proficiency and self-esteem, as well as the need for clear rules and guidelines to control negative class participation. Understanding these distinctive characteristics is crucial for foreign language teachers to navigate classroom management effectively. The evolution of teaching approaches in foreign language education has seen a shift from grammar-based methodologies to more communicative approaches. Grammar-based methods emphasize grammar rules, translation, and deductive teaching, while communicative approaches focus on learning to communicate and achieving communicative competence through interaction. These changes in teaching methods impact classroom management by influencing student-teacher interactions, participation, and the use of the target language.

Foreign language teaching, specially Italian language involves distinct characteristics that influence classroom management. Effective instruction requires the use of a language that students do not yet understand, necessitates interaction patterns, and employs diverse, student-focused teaching methodologies. These features affect how teachers manage their classrooms and create specific challenges related to students' language proficiency and self-esteem, as well as the need for clear rules and guidelines to control negative class participation. Other studies in foreign language education have examined various aspects related to classroom management. For example, some studies have explored the use of the first language (L1) and the target language (TL) in foreign language education and the impact it has on classroom management. These studies have established a clear connection between L1 or FL use and other aspects of teaching, including classroom management. Additionally, research has focused on the influence of previous teacher preparation coursework on how teachers manage their classrooms. These studies have examined the relationship between teacher

training and classroom management practices in foreign language education. Furthermore, research has investigated the unique classroom management issues that foreign language teachers face, such as inaudible responses, lack of respect for foreign language study, and including heritage language speakers in classes. These studies provide insights into the specific challenges and dynamics of managing foreign language classrooms. Finally, some studies have explored alternatives and strategies for reducing the negative impact of classroom management problems in foreign language classes. These studies suggest approaches such as building rapport, developing awareness-raising activities, and valuing students as individuals to create a positive learning environment. Overall, these studies contribute to the understanding of classroom management in foreign language education and provide recommendations for effective practices. Findings in Farrell's (2003) study focused on the different phases a teacher went through during their first year of teaching. Initially, the teacher had high ideals and wanted to make a difference in their students' lives. However, they experienced shock when faced with the realities of the classroom. This led to the teacher seeking quick fixes for discipline problems, but they still encountered difficulties with the class and communication with colleagues. As the first year progressed, the teacher began to cope better with their teaching methods and classroom management.

Classroom Management Problems in Foreign Language Education

Studies and research in the area of classroom management in foreign language education have sought to provide ways to reduce the impact of classroom management problems. One study by Soares (2007) focused on reducing negative class participation by building rapport and implementing awareness-raising activities. The author emphasized the importance of valuing students as individuals and helping them understand their responsibility in creating a positive learning environment. Another study by Quintero and Ramírez (2011) identified strategies such as maintaining students' attention, providing a variety of activities, and managing time wisely to deal with discipline problems. Castellanos (2002) suggested strategies such as focusing, monitoring, and modeling, which contribute to better classroom management. These studies highlight the significance of self-esteem, fair treatment, and student involvement in creating a positive classroom environment. Further research is needed to explore the connection between classroom management issues and teaching methods used in foreign language instruction. Teachers themselves can play a crucial role in conducting research on classroom management issues in their own classrooms, enhancing their professional development. The review also calls for more research specifically on the impact of target language use in managing the foreign language classroom. Despite the availability of books on classroom management in general education, there is a scarcity of books specifically addressing classroom management in foreign language education from a theoretical or research standpoint. Many alternative strategies suggested in the studies reviewed

come from teachers' own experiences or established ideas in the literature. Teacher preparation programs should continue to explore theories and practices that address classroom management issues in foreign language education.

The review acknowledges that there are unique aspects of foreign language teaching that can impact classroom management. These aspects include target language use, interaction patterns, teaching methods, the inclusion of heritage speakers, and the lack of respect for foreign language study. These factors can influence how classroom management is approached and may require foreign language teachers to develop specific skills to address these challenges. However, there is a lack of research on how these distinctive aspects directly impact classroom management in foreign language education. Further research is needed to understand and address these issues.

Conclusion

Classroom management and challenges in learning Italian as a foreign language at the Ismail Qemali, University of Vlora require careful consideration to ensure effective language instruction. By implementing effective classroom management strategies and addressing the unique challenges faced by learners, teachers can create an engaging and supportive environment for students to thrive in their Italian language journey. Through research-based approaches, ongoing professional development, and collaboration with colleagues, the Department of Foreign Languages can enhance the language learning experience, preparing students for success in their future endeavors. Motivation plays a vital role in language learning. By understanding the nature of motivation and factors that influence it, educators can create supportive learning environments and implement strategies to foster students' motivation. With motivated learners, language learning becomes more enjoyable, effective, and sustainable. Therefore, it is essential to prioritize students' motivation and tailor teaching approaches accordingly to facilitate their language learning journey.

References

1. Burnett, J. J. (2011). Exploring the relationship between teacher beliefs and styles on classroom management in relation to actual teaching practices: a case study. *Procedia: Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(1), 612-617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2009.01.109>
2. Eveyik-Aydin, E., Kurt, G., & Mede, E. (2009). Exploring the relationship between teacher beliefs and styles on class-room management in relation to actual teaching practices: a case study. *Procedia: Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(1), 612-617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2009.01.109>
3. Farrell, T. S. C. (2003). Learning to teach English language during the first year: Personal influences and challenges. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 19(1), 95-111. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(02\)00088-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(02)00088-4)
4. Farrell, T. S. C. (2006). The first year of language teaching: Imposing order. *System*, 34(2), 211-221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2005.12.001>

5. Farrell, T. S. C. (2008). Classroom management. New York, us: tesol International Association.
6. Marzano, R. J., Gaddy, B. B., Foseid, M., Foseid, M., & Marzano, J. S. (2005). Classroom management that works: Research-based strategies for every teacher. Ontario, Canada: Pembroke Publishers Limited.
7. Scrivener, J. (2012). Classroom management techniques. Cambridge, uk: Cambridge University Press.
8. Soares, D. (2007). Discipline problems in the efl class: Is there a cure? Profile: Issues in Teachers' Professional Development, 8(1), 41-58.
9. Wright, T. (2005). Classroom management in language education. New York, us: Palgrave MacMillan. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230514188>.
10. Clement, M. C. (2013). Pop Quiz: Classroom Management Strategies. Educational Horizons, 92(1),24–25.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0013175x1309200112>
11. Gunter, P. L., & Denny, R. K. (1996). Research Issues and Needs regarding Teacher use of Classroom Management Strategies. Behavioral Disorders,22(1),15–20.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/019874299602200102>
12. Aksu, N. (2015, August 30). Albanian Teachers' Approaches to Classroom Management. European Journal of Social Sciences Education and Research, 4(1),186<http://dx.doi.org/10.26417/ejser.v4i1.p186-194>